

The Development and Implementation of an Automated Construction and Demolition Waste Sorting Prototype

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Abstract: This paper introduces an innovative prototype system for Construction and Demolition Waste (CDW) sorting, integrating deep learning models and robotic arm manipulators. The system utilizes the YOLO deep learning architecture to accurately identify and locate CDW materials such as concrete, brick, and tile. A vast dataset ensures the system's understanding of CDW variability. Robotic arms, guided by deep learning models, perform precise pick-and-place actions on a conveyor belt, enabling efficient sorting for recycling or disposal. The paper outlines the design, development, and performance evaluation of the CDW sorting prototype, highlighting its potential to enhance efficiency, accuracy, and sustainability in construction waste management.

1. Introduction

The construction and demolition industry faces a substantial challenge in managing the considerable amount of waste it generates, posing implications for both waste management practices and environmental sustainability (Marzouk, 2014; Menegaki 2018). Recognizing the escalating awareness of waste's environmental impact and the imperative to adopt more sustainable waste management strategies, a series of innovative waste sorting systems have been developed. The prototype introduced in this research represents a pioneering solution addressing the complexities of waste management. This system has the potential to enhance sorting efficiency and accuracy, mitigate environmental impact, and render waste management more economically feasible.

2. Automation in CDW sorting process

The implementation of an automated construction and demolition sorting system stands to revolutionize key parameters. It expeditiously sorts waste materials into distinct categories,

reducing reliance on manual labour, while accurately identifying the type of waste generated. Moreover, it contributes to enhanced safety by minimizing the risk of worker injuries and exposure to inhalation hazards (Sarc, R.,2019). Additionally, the system ensures comprehensive data management by tracking the quantity and types of recycled waste, thereby fostering sustainability goals through the reduction of overall waste, improved recycling rates, and the conservation of valuable resources. Automation in CDW sorting often involves the deployment of advanced sensor-based technologies, such as near-infrared sensors and hyperspectral imaging (Wen Xiao, 2020), enabling real-time identification and segregation of diverse materials on conveyor belts. These technologies contribute to accelerated sorting speeds and improved accuracy compared to manual methods.

Furthermore, robotic systems equipped with artificial intelligence (AI) and computer vision are gaining traction. These systems utilize advanced algorithms to recognize and sort CDW materials efficiently. Notably, deep learning models exhibit remarkable prowess in identifying and categorizing a wide array of CDW materials (Xinxing Chen, 2022).

3.1. Hardware configuration of the Automated CDW sorting prototype

The prototype of the Construction and Demolition Waste Separation System, developed in this project, consists of an industrial camera, overlooking the workspace, a conveyor belt which carries the rubble, two robotic manipulators for the waste separation and a dedicated local PC. Adjacent to the conveyor belt, six loading trays are strategically positioned. Each robot is allocated three loading trays, and each tray is designated for a specific material type - specifically, concrete, brick, and tile. This meticulous arrangement ensures a systematic and efficient sorting process, facilitating the precise categorization of materials during the waste sorting operation in the construction and demolition waste prototype.

Figure 1. The CDW sorting prototype.

3.1. Vision System

The imaging component of the waste sorting prototype is an HIKROBOT GigE Area Scan colour camera, chosen for its specific capabilities in the context of construction and demolition waste sorting. The camera features a 2.3-megapixel Sony IMX249 sensor, providing detailed visual data essential for precise object identification. With 41 frames per second, it ensures real-time image capture, contributing to the prototype's efficiency in dynamic waste

sorting environments. The camera, mounted on the frame of the conveyor belt, is positioned 1.2 meters above the scanning surface, strategically placed beyond the robots' working reach

3.2. Conveyor belt

The conveyor belt system used in the construction and demolition waste sorting prototype is a crucial component designed for optimal performance. Comprising a straight frame Dorner conveyor customized to dimensions of 1.5 meters in length and 45 cm in width, the system prioritizes efficiency and precision. Ensuring robust stability, the conveyor belt is securely attached to an aluminium frame firmly mounted on the ground. Powering this system is a stepper motor, selected for its ability to provide heightened precision in operation. To maximize torque, a gearbox is strategically affixed to the motor shaft. Facilitating seamless control, the stepper motor is managed by a dedicated controller, which oversees speed, direction, and torque. This controller consists of a bipolar stepper driver and a microcontroller, allowing for fine-tuned adjustments in the conveyor's operation.

The conveyor belt surface is divided into three notional sectors; the camera capture area and the two robot working spaces. A buffer zone is defined between the two work spaces for robot collision avoidance.

Figure 2. The conveyor belt.

3.3. Robotic Manipulators

The robotic manipulators are Automata Eva Robot Arms having six degrees of freedom and controlled through python software.

Robotic movements are achieved by instructing the robot to execute a single Toolpath for a fixed number of cycles, which is the number of rubbles assigned to the robot to pick. Toolpaths consist of a series of Waypoints along a Timeline, each specifying the position and

orientation for the robot's end-effector and, if used, the input/output state of the digital controller integrated at the base of the robot.

Although Waypoints correspond to specific locations in the robot's workspace their definition is done in terms of joint angles. A robot movement is managed by rotating each joint of the robot (6 joints in total). A robotic manipulator cannot sense the Cartesian coordinates so the coordinates need to be translated to robot joint angles with the use of inverse kinematics (Singh,2017). Therefore, for each target location received from the vision system, the microprocessor of the robotic manipulator will have to perform inverse kinematics to calculate the joint configuration.

Each robot is assigned three dropping points, which are trays for the collection of specific material types; concrete brick and tile. These dropping points along with the stand-by position and the home position of the robot are predefined locations and hence constant joint configurations. The end-effector orientation is kept in a constant downward position to eliminate the need of realigning it with the conveyor surface, therefore reducing further kinematics calculations and consequently reducing processing time.

3.4. Soft gripper end-effector

Attached to the end-effector of each robotic arm is a SoftRobotics "mGrip" soft gripper. The "mGrip" gripper consists of soft fingers, made of soft elastomers, that are pneumatically inflated and controlled to facilitate the effortless retrieval of objects. It enables facile retrieval of unstructured items, irrespective of their geometric attributes, surface characteristics, orientation, and edge profiles (Rithvik, 2023; Shintake 2018). Notably, it obviates the necessity for aligning the robotic end-effector with the object's orientation, eliminating the need for supplementary sensors or intricate numerical computations (Yue-Dong Ku, 2020). This capability greatly enhances the program execution time response. Furthermore, the "mGrip" soft gripper allows objects to be picked up from their base, with a clearance of just one millimetre above the conveyor belt, without necessitating the calculation of the object's height, thus obviating the need for 3D image analysis. The opening and closing actions of each gripper are initiated via a pressure regulator and a pneumatic solenoid valve, which is under the control of the robot base's digital output port.

Figure 3. The "mGrip" gripper.

4. Methodology of automating the waste sorting process

The automated sorting process of Construction and Demolition Waste (CDW) commences with the initiation of the conveyor belt. This conveyor system transports rubble systematically beneath a camera at a constant speed and direction. The camera conducts a surface scan, and an Artificial Intelligence (AI) system, utilizing deep learning image processing, performs detection. The AI system identifies the rubble, categorizes it based on material type, calculates its coordinates on the conveyor belt's surface, and segregates it into two distinct groups corresponding to the workspace of each robotic manipulator. Subsequently, the conveyor belt halts, and all pertinent information from the AI is transmitted to the robotic manipulators to implement a Toolpath in accordance with the received data.

Figure 4 illustrates the Toolpath that each robot is required to execute. Upon receiving information about the number, material type, and coordinates of the designated rubble, each robot commences the process by employing inverse kinematics to compute the joint configuration necessary to reach the specified location. The robotic end-effector is programmed to approach and retreat from each target position by initially maintaining a distance from the conveyor belt's surface and then ascending vertically. This methodology prevents the inadvertent displacement of rubble with the gripper during approach and mitigates the risk of friction between grasped objects and the conveyor belt surface.

Once a piece of rubble is grasped, it is deposited into the tray corresponding to the material type indicated by the AI system. Each robot iteratively repeats this process, executing a loop for the predetermined number of times required to pick up the assigned rubble quantity.

Figure 4. The robot Toolpath.

5. Supervised Deep Learning Vision process

In the context of CDW sorting, the training of the YOLOv7 (You only look once, version 7) model is a crucial component of the supervised deep learning vision process. The model development approach involves feeding a diverse dataset of annotated images, which

encompasses various types of CDW materials under different lighting and orientation conditions, into the YOLOv7 training pipeline.

As the model undergoes training, it learns to discern distinct features and characteristics of various waste materials, such as texture, colour, and shape. This is achieved through multiple layers of convolutional neural networks, which enable the extraction and learning of hierarchical feature representations. To enhance the model's robustness and accuracy, techniques like data augmentation, transfer learning, and fine-tuning are employed. Data augmentation involves altering the training images in ways that mimic real-world variations, such as changes in scale, rotation, and lighting conditions. Transfer learning leverages pre-trained weights on large datasets to improve learning efficiency and performance, especially when the available CDW dataset is limited. The culmination of this training process equips the YOLOv7 model with the ability to reliably and swiftly detect and classify various types of CDW on a moving conveyor belt, thereby facilitating efficient and automated sorting in waste management systems. Figure 5 presents samples of concrete, brick and tiles identified on the conveyor belt by the YOLOv7 model.

Figure 5. Samples of concrete, bricks and tiles identified on a conveyor belt.

6. Evaluation of CDW sorting prototype

The Testing and Validation phase within the project's objectives yielded valuable results, affirming the effectiveness of the CDW sorting prototype. In accuracy testing, the YOLO-based object detection model attained the best accuracy ($mAP_{50:95} \approx 70\%$) at the highest inference speed (Demetriou, 2023). The model achieved an inference speed of 25 ms when tested on an Nvidia Tesla T4 (16 GB memory) GPU. Notably, the model exhibited robustness in handling challenging scenarios, correctly identifying and classifying stacked and adhered CDW samples.

Robustness and reliability testing underscored the system's adaptability to diverse conditions. It consistently maintained accuracy levels under varying lighting conditions, fluctuations in waste material composition, and different degrees of congestion on the conveyor belt.

Integrated system testing demonstrated seamless interaction and coordination among components. The holistic approach ensured effective operation, with the computer vision

system, robotic manipulators, and conveyor belt working in tandem. The system performed exceptionally well in simulated CDW sorting environments, achieving an overall sorting accuracy of 100%.

7. Conclusions

In this study a CDW sorting prototype has been constructed and implemented. It is a low cost and small-scale prototype that provided the proof of concept. It allowed the Implementation of Supervised Deep Learning Vision System in real time and the optimization of programming and physical parameters.

The evaluation results collectively validate the efficacy and reliability of the CDW sorting prototype, showcasing its potential for real-world applications in construction and demolition waste management.

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9. References

- Demetris Demetriou, Pavlos Mavromatidis, Ponsian M. Robert, Harris Papadopoulos, Michael F. Petrou, Demetris Nicolaides (2023), *Real-time construction demolition waste detection using state-of-the-art deep learning methods; single-stage vs two-stage detectors*, Waste Management Journal, Volume 167, pp 194-203.
- Jun Shintake, Vito Cacucciolo, Dario Floreano, Herbert Shea (2018), *Soft Robotic Grippers*, Advanced Materials, Volume 30, Issue 29.
- Maria Menegaki, Dimitris Damigos, (2018), *A review on current situation and challenges of construction and demolition waste management*, Current Opinion in Green and Sustainable Chemistry, Volume 13, pp 8-15.
- Mohamed Marzouk, Shimaa Azab, (2014), *Environmental and economic impact assessment of construction and demolition waste disposal using system dynamics*, Resources, Conservation and Recycling, Volume 82, pp 41-49.
- Sarc, R., Curtis, A., Kandlbauer, L., Khodier, K., Lorber, K.E., Pomberger, R., (2019). *Digitalisation and intelligent robotics in value chain of circular economy oriented waste management – A review*. Waste Management 95.

S. Rithvik, Vijith Rai, Surya Dornal, Deepak J. and B.C. Pramod (2023), Soft Robotics in Waste Management, Self-Powered Cyber Physical Systems, Wiley Online Library, pp 341-348.

Tarun Pratap Singh, P. Suresh, Swet Chandan (2017), Forward and Inverse Kinematic Analysis of Robotic Manipulators, International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET), Volume 4, Issue 2, pp 1459 - 1469.

Wen Xiao, Jianhong Yang, Huaiying Fang, Jiangteng Zhuang, Yuedong Ku, Xiaojun Zhang, (2020), Development of an automatic sorting robot for construction and demolition waste, Clean Technologies and Environmental Policy, Issue 9, pp 1829-1841.

Xinxing Chen, Huaiyang Huang, Yuxuan Liu, Jiqing Li, Ming Liu, (2022), Robot for automatic waste sorting on construction sites, Automation in Construction, Volume 141.

Yue-Dong Ku, Jian-Hong Yang, Huai-Ying Fang, Wen Xiao, Jiang-Teng Zhuang, (2020) *Optimization of Grasping Efficiency of a Robot Used for Sorting Construction and Demolition Waste*, International Journal of Automation and Computing Volume 17, pp 691–700.